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The development of fintech applications as a condition for advancing the non-state pension provision system

KEYWORDS

fintech application,
non-state pension provision,
pension, long-term savings,
co-financing,
pension savings market

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The development of the non-state pension provision system is crucial for enhancing the financial stability of citizens in old age, reducing the burden on the state pension fund, and ensuring a more dignified standard of living for retirees. This contributes to the diversification of income sources and fosters greater individual responsibility for future pensions.

The study is aimed at developing a conceptual model for a pension planning application that facilitates the creation of personalized retirement strategies. The model incorporates continuous monitoring of legislative, economic, and other changes to provide citizens with an additional tool for independently building long-term savings.

Materials and methods. The study used the following materials: legislative and regulatory frameworks governing the operations of non-state pension funds (NPFs) and fintech development; scientific publications and articles in the fields of financial technology, pension provision, and information systems. The methods used in the study included analysis of legal and regulatory frameworks; case studies of fintech application development and implementation in NPFs.

Results. The AKPIN fintech application enables the formation of personalized strategies for pension savings and supports the long-term development of the funded component of Russia's pension system. The proposed application can analyze user data and provide tailored recommendations for increasing savings. If a user decides to withdraw funds, the application can also generate advice upon request. By continuously monitoring news, financial regulators' actions, economic indicators, and legislative changes, the application offers up-to-date recommendations, assisting users in making informed individual decisions regarding the management of their pension savings.

Conclusion. Fintech applications can make pension services more accessible to a broader audience by offering a user-friendly interface for managing retirement savings.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this article stems primarily from the growing public interest in non-state pension provision. Amid economic instability and ongoing reforms in the pension system, citizens are increasingly seeking alternative ways to secure financial stability in old age.

Modern technologies enable the automation and simplification of many pension-related processes. In this context, fintech applications enhance the convenience and transparency of interactions with non-state pension funds (NPFs), thereby fostering the development of the non-state pension system.

The development of innovative fintech applications can serve as a competitive tool for NPFs, allowing them to differentiate themselves in the market. These applications can also improve the financial literacy of NPF clients by providing information on pension programs, facilitating future pension calculations, and offering optimization strategies for retirement savings. Integrating fintech applications with other financial services – such as banking apps and investment platforms – enables a more holistic approach to personal finance management.

Globally, financial technologies are increasingly transforming societal norms and have become a key driver of modernization in social welfare systems, significantly improving the efficiency of socio-economic relations. For instance, in Kazakhstan, the Unified Accumulative Pension Fund (UAPF) addresses pension system expansion through improved service channels, digitalization, and public awareness campaigns. However, its effectiveness has been hindered by low household incomes, limited financial literacy among insured individuals, and regulatory constraints. To overcome these challenges, the UAPF has streamlined registration processes, developed multi-channel services, and introduced online client applications [1].

Social security systems worldwide continue to face challenges due to rising client expectations, aging populations, technological advancements, and structural labor market shifts. The digital revolution and modern technological solutions present unique opportunities to enhance the targeting of financial support and expand coverage for those in need. However, the digitalization of social welfare requires additional efforts in retraining and upskilling a significant portion of the workforce to adapt to new labor conditions.

At the moment, fintech [2] can be perceived as a driver of the development of pension savings markets in Russia and abroad. Innovative financial solutions not

only help preserve capital over the long term but also enable its growth, thereby benefiting both younger generations and retirees.

Among the most pressing fundamental challenges in the development strategy of the Russian pension system are the imbalance of the Social Fund of Russia (SFR), the lagging adjustments of labor pensions compared to average wage growth and the relatively low standard of living among older generations. These issues, combined with existing demographic risks, pose a major challenge to Russia's social security system. According to Rosstat, the pension replacement rate (average pension relative to average wages) in Russia stood at 27.3% in 2022, with a steady decline since 2013 (-6 percentage points over nine years) [3]. Addressing these problems requires a comprehensive approach, incorporating innovative conceptual and technological solutions to develop non-state pension infrastructure, and behavioral shifts among the population toward greater personal involvement in building retirement savings.

This study is aimed at developing and substantiating a conceptual framework for advancing a financial-investment model of non-state pension provision based on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies.

The study proposes leveraging GPT-3.5 and higher for collecting, processing, and systematizing big data related to non-state pension finance through platforms like Rationale. An AI-powered service with a financial-investment model for personalized pension planning will address the following challenges: encouraging citizens to engage in long-term financial planning; motivating rational increases in savings rates and long-term investments; eliminating barriers stemming from insufficient competencies, time, knowledge, or information for effective household-level decision-making in building personal and family retirement-investment capital. The long-term implementation of this software solution is expected to boost aggregate income levels among older generations, sustain high consumer demand amid Russia's aging population, as well as support stable economic growth under international sanctions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

M. Cho et al. argue that a reliable and adequate pension system helps individuals understand its mechanics, set realistic expectations for future benefits, and adjust current savings behavior to plan for a secure and comfortable retirement [4].

S. Kim identifies barriers to private pension program development and outlines prerequisites for their promotion. The author emphasizes that tax incentives and employer/employee subsidies significantly enhance the appeal of private pension products, while financial literacy is a critical factor influencing participation and returns [5].

J. A. Turner analyzes the impact of population aging on pension policies in the United States and other high-income countries, including debates on raising the social security eligibility age [6].

A. Ananta and E. N. Arifin highlight that in less developed economies like Indonesia, retirement often leads to poverty. The Indonesian government is considering a shift from the current PAYG (pay-as-you-go) system to a fully funded defined-contribution model, though the authors caution that this should complement but not replace existing PAYG systems [7].

M. Dorofeev and K. Tamashiro stress the need to adapt pension models to global economic challenges by improving social welfare services, optimizing public finance management, and harnessing technological advancements developed by Industry 4.0 to mitigate risks to pension systems [8].

L. Drobyshevskaya et al. identify key issues affecting the development of the Russian Federation's pension system through comparative MMGI analysis, advocating for a digital matrix and an open, user-friendly platform to unify stakeholders [9].

M. E. Valishina and E. N. Valishin examine contemporary digitalization trends and their application in the NPFs investment practices. The authors argue that most Russians today are not passive citizens and they actively seek ways to generate additional income during retirement. The researchers propose measures to overcome systemic constraints, including expanding the range of permitted investment instruments for pension reserves, improving pension accumulation investment strategies, and refining requirements for insurance reserve allocation in the context of economic digitalization [10].

V. N. Tandon et al. analyze the cloud-based SAMPANN system designed to eliminate intermediaries and facilitate direct pension payments to retirees. The authors highlight the potential for developing automated, scalable cloud software for pension processing, authorization, approval and disbursement that could eventually serve all departments regardless of their functional differences [11].

A. Abdullah et al. believe that financial literacy is key to ensuring personal and family economic stability. Failures in financial planning often leave retirees without

sufficient means to meet their financial needs. The authors offer a novel perspective on retirement financial planning literacy among Malaysian pensioners [12].

A. Anderson et al. demonstrate a correlation between financial literacy and retirement savings/planning, while emphasizing the importance of understanding the gap between self-perceived and actual financial literacy levels [13].

J. Binswanger and K. G. Carman show that individuals who plan for retirement accumulate greater retirement wealth. The planning process, i.e., the decision-making sequence, creates a positive relationship between “planning” and wealth accumulation. The authors identify three decision-making approaches: literal planning, rules of thumb, and unsystematic methods. Their findings confirm that planning has an economically significant impact on wealth accumulation, with non-planners saving substantially less. They suggest that simple, rules-based financial planning advice could benefit those lacking systematic approaches [14].

J. M. Collins et al. find that informational interventions increase reported participation in pension plans, emergency savings, and budget utilization. Workers with access to financial education increased their actual retirement deferrals by 26 dollars per month, demonstrating that retirement education programs can effectively enhance retirement planning [15].

M. Dolls et al. document that since 2005, Germany’s pension administration has sent annual letters containing detailed, comprehensible information about the pension system and individual expected state pension benefits. The authors found that labor incomes being the most direct way to increase state pensions rose as a result of this information campaign [16].

A. M. Barrett and B. Whelan emphasize the importance of pension literacy, revealing that two-thirds of older Irish adults do not know their expected pension amount or whether payments will be lump-sum, monthly, or both [17].

E. C. Brüggen et al. argue that technological services like advanced online pension planners can positively influence retirement planning engagement. They suggest that new service technologies offer opportunities to accommodate individual differences, for instance, by integrating fewer interactive features for women than men in pension planners. Furthermore, cognitive engagement should be stimulated through relevant, interesting and valuable information integration [18].

D. McCloskey and M. McDonnell demonstrate that interventions helping individuals visualize their future can increase retirement savings. Most study participants

acknowledged their savings rates were too low for comfortable retirement and consequently increased their pension contributions [19].

Investment income also constitutes an important pension revenue stream, dependent on factors like investment strategies, economic conditions, and government regulation [20].

Thus, while digitalization trends in NPF investment practices are highly relevant, they remain underdeveloped in academic literature. Automated pension processing software and other fintech solutions are presented only fragmentarily.

Based on the analysis, recommendations and proposals can be developed to improve the development and implementation of fintech applications in the non-state pension system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study utilized the following materials: legislative and regulatory documents governing the operations of NPFs and the development of financial technologies; scholarly publications and research articles in the fields of financial technologies, pension systems, and information systems (including but not limited to International Handbooks of Population, Journal of Financial Economics, Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization, Economic Inquiry, Journal of Public Economics, Journal of Aging and Social Policy, and Journal of Services Marketing).

The methods used in the study included analysis of the regulatory framework to identify key factors and constraints affecting fintech application development and implementation within the non-state pension system, systematic evaluation of specific fintech application projects developed and deployed by NPFs.

RESULTS

Implementation of a digital application for developing the non-state pension provision system

State programs for developing the non-state social security sector are crucial for creating comprehensive solutions to existing pension provision challenges in various countries. The target audience of programs involving government co-financing mechanisms primarily consists of citizens opting for passive investment strategies. However, among both younger and older generations, there is a growing number

of individuals who, under certain conditions, could independently engage in personal pension and investment planning, as well as active management of their retirement finances.

The concept of implementing digital applications for pension fund management is being actively explored abroad, as most developed countries face similar challenges of aging populations. However, unlike the Russian Federation, many Western countries also grapple with additional issues related to financial stability, fiscal balance, and debt sustainability. A prominent example of such digital pension management solutions is the Swedish application “minPension” [21]. This real-time platform enables personalized pension planning with flexible withdrawal periods tailored to individual retirement needs [22]. Such solutions demonstrate significant practical potential, particularly among younger generations in the context of social sector digitalization [23].

This study proposes the development of an innovative software platform called AKPIN, designed to assist citizens in planning and managing their pension savings, investment portfolios, and social benefits. The platform employs AI, including the GPT-3.5 model, to provide personalized recommendations and information on pension-related matters (Fig. 1) [24; 25]. The system operates using: (1) GPT-based search technologies for big data collection, processing, and systematization, and (2) Rationale-type services for pension projection calculations.

The AKPIN application functions as a pension planner that analyzes users' financial status and progress toward their goals while generating timely recommendations in response to changes in legislation, economic conditions, financial regulators' actions, and other relevant factors.

Within the AKPIN application ecosystem, clients undergo a comprehensive assessment of their socioeconomic status, investment profile, and risk tolerance. This automated process identifies optimal opportunities for participation in various government-sponsored financial support programs. The service provides tailored guidance on required documentation and strategic actions to maximize economic benefits when managing personal retirement finances.

The client path is as follows (Fig. 2): the user launches the application and initiates registration by providing personal data (full name, date of birth, contact information, etc.). For authentication, the application can use various methods, including SMS or email, to confirm information.

Figure 1 Example of AI dialogue

Source: compiled by the authors

After successful registration, the user fills out a detailed questionnaire covering financial objectives, current income/ expenditure patterns, and investment preferences. The neural network generates personalized investment and pension planning recommendations based on data analysis and predictive modeling. Recommendations are visualized through interactive graphs, charts, and dashboards, providing clear projections of long-term retirement savings growth. The

user can accept or reject the recommendations provided by the application. The system performs pension amount simulations based on selected strategies. Periodic notifications and reminders prompt users to review, update, and execute their plans, followed by revised recommendations.

Figure 2 The concept of the application from the client side

Source: compiled by the authors using the BPMN model

The financial market institutions responsible for implementing citizens' pension plans include investment companies, NPFs, commercial banks, and insurance providers. Accumulation instruments may comprise corporate pension plans, unit-linked and investment-linked insurance products (NSZh/ISZh), securities, deposits, derivative and structured financial instruments, as well as various modern trading strategies [26]. However, all instruments must be approved by the Central Bank of Russia.

Engaging younger generations in active management of personal retirement finances [27] can be achieved through several approaches: (1) conducting lectures and financial workshops; (2) utilizing a "best practices repository" where qualified experts share their experience in strategy development; (3) creating video content using neural networks (Pictory.ai); (4) employing open-source codes and application integration capabilities with the Central Bank's Marketplace technologies and the digital ruble.

The application can be deployed through various channels, including government services (within the framework of the Central Bank Online application, on federal and regional open budget data portals, and platforms such as Active Citizen), as well as through personal accounts on the public services portal of the Russian Federation, and in a separate private application.

Consider a simplified example of the application operation. (1) Initial conditions: Viktor Petrovich, a lead engineer with a net salary of 93,000 rubles after income tax, has 10 years of work experience and is 37 years old. After registering in the AKPIN application, he configured his personal pension plan parameters according to his strategy (selecting the most conservative option without recommendations for purchasing securities, foreign currencies, or structured financial instruments). Viktor Petrovich aims to accumulate 3,500,000 rubles by retirement to maintain a monthly income not less than the regional average wage. Currently, he has 500,000 rubles in personal savings. On 08/01/2024, the application generated a plan to achieve his financial goal, recommending: depositing 300,000 rubles in Bank X by 08/07/2024 at 8.2% annual interest, and allocating 100,000 rubles to a brokerage account with an IIA to be replenished monthly by 25,000 rubles for tax deductions. (2) Pension-investment strategy revision: In October 2023, when the Central Bank raised its key rate to 15% annually, the application recommended that Viktor Petrovich close his 8.2% deposit in Bank X after 9 months and open a 1-year deposit in Bank Y (automatically verified as systemically important, consistent with his conservative approach) at 14.1% annual interest for 300,000 rubles plus an additional 100,000 rubles accumulated due to his 15% salary increase. This recommendation allowed Viktor Petrovich to earn approximately 24,000 rubles more by reallocating his 300,000-ruble savings to a longer-term, higher-yield deposit. Most individuals neither actively monitor nor capitalize on emerging financial market opportunities, nor do they adequately assess risks, resulting in suboptimal management of their savings. The proposed software product can serve as a reliable financial advisor, not only improving average personal savings management outcomes but also enhancing the financial market's functional efficiency by increasing the prevalence of timely and rational decision-making across the market.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The authors propose the development of a fintech solution called AKPIN that enables the creation of personalized investment strategies while supporting the long-

term development of the funded component of Russia's pension system. This service will function not merely as a "smart calculator", but as an educational platform for enhancing financial literacy. Client data updates will automatically feed into the system, which generates real-time financial recommendations with explanatory insights detailing why users should follow the AI's suggestions while outlining potential risks and alternative financial strategies tailored to individual circumstances. Continuous monitoring of news cycles, financial regulator actions, market indicators, and legislative changes ensures the relevance of recommendations and facilitates effective personalized decision-making regarding Russian citizens' pension savings management. This innovation will complement existing mechanisms for personal long-term savings accumulation. The new long-term savings program, replacing the former state pension co-financing program, incentivizes citizens to make voluntary contributions toward their funded pension component. Modern individuals, being particularly younger generations under 35, increasingly prefer active personal capital management. Consequently, creating favorable conditions for developing savings behaviors that meet contemporary challenges and ensure adequate post-retirement living standards has become particularly relevant.

The study concludes that fintech applications can significantly improve pension service accessibility by offering user-friendly interfaces for retirement savings management. Modern solutions provide personalized recommendations, streamline interactions with pension funds, and enhance overall customer satisfaction. Key advantages of fintech applications in non-state pension systems include the automation of routine operations, integration with banking/investment platforms, customized pension planning, financial literacy improvement, and expanded access to investment instruments. The proposed solution demonstrates how technological innovation can optimize both individual retirement outcomes and systemic efficiency in pension fund management.

REFERENCES

1. MACO. Social security priority. *Development of management practices*. Available at: <https://www.issa.int/sites/default/files/documents/2022-04/5-priorities-report-Europe-WEB.pdf> (accessed 13 november 2023).
2. *Development of financial technologies*. Available at: <https://www.cbr.ru/fintech/> (accessed 13 november 2023).
3. *Federal State Statistics Service*. Older generation. Available at: <https://rosstat.gov.ru/folder/13877> (accessed 12 november 2023).
4. Cho, M., Nicolini, G., & Lee, H. (2022). The National Pension Systems and Financial Consumers: An International Comparative Perspective on the Key Linkages. In: Lee, H., Nicolini, G., Cho, M. (eds) *International Comparison of Pension Systems. Contributions to Management Science*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6446-6_1

5. Kim, S. (2022). Role of the Private Pension Programs. In: Lee, H., Nicolini, G., Cho, M. (eds) *International Comparison of Pension Systems. Contributions to Management Science*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6446-6_13
6. Turner, J. A. (2022). Pension Policies. In: May, J. F., Goldstone, J. A. (eds) *International Handbook of Population Policies. International Handbooks of Population, vol 11*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-02040-7_26
7. Ananta, A., & Arifin, E. N. (2023). Fully Funded Defined Contribution Pension System. In: *Handbook of Aging, Health and Public Policy*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-1914-4_175-1
8. Dorofeev, M., & Tamashiro, K. (2023). Evolution of Pension System Financial Models for Sustainable Economic Growth. In: Dincer, H., Yüksel, S. (eds) *Economic Development and the Environmental Ecosystem. Contributions to Economics*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-26596-9_14
9. Drobyshevskaya, L., Mamiy, E., Chulkov, A., & Timchenko, A. (2022). Improving the Efficiency of the Pension System in the Digital Economy. In: Antipova, T. (eds) *Digital Science. DSIC 2021. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 381*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93677-8_43
10. Valishina, M. E., & Valishin, E. N. (2022). Economy Digitalization of Russia: Non-state Pension Funds and Their Social Orientation. In: Ashmarina, S. I., Mantulenko, V. V. (eds) *Digital Technologies in the New Socio-Economic Reality. ISCDTE 2021. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 304*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-83175-2_75
11. Tandon, V. N. et al. (2023). SAMPANN: Automated System for Pension Disbursal in India (Case Study: BSNL VRS Pension Disbursal). In: Choudrie, J., Mahalle, P., Perumal, T., Joshi, A. (eds) *IOT with Smart Systems. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, vol 312*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3575-6_61
12. Abdullah, A. et al. (2023). Financial Planning Literacy Among Retirees: Issues and Challenges. In: Mansour, N., Bujosa Vadell, L. M. (eds) *Finance, Accounting and Law in the Digital Age. Contributions to Management Science*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27296-7_50
13. Anderson, A., Baker, F., & Robinson, D. T. (2017). Precautionary savings, retirement planning, and misperceptions of financial literacy. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 126(2), 383–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2017.07.008>
14. Binswanger, J., & Carman, K. G. (2012). How real people make long-term decisions: the case of retirement preparation. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 81(1), 39–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2011.08.010>
15. Collins, JM., & Urban, C. (2016). The role of information on Retirement Planning: Evidence from a field study. *Economic Inquiry*, 54(4), 1860–1872. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecin.12349>
16. Dolls, M., Doerrenberg, P., Peichl, A., & Stichnoth, H. (2018). Do retirement savings increase in response to information about retirement and expected pensions? *Journal of Public Economics*, 158, 168–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2017.12.014>
17. Barrett, A. M., & Whelan, B. (2015). How well-informed are pension scheme members on their future pension BENEFITS? Evidence from Ireland. *Journal of Aging & Social Policy*, 295–313. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959420.2015.1044817>
18. Brügger, EC., Post, T., & Schmitz, K. (2019). Interactivity in online pension planners enhances engagement with retirement planning – but not for everyone. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 33(4), 488–501. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-02-2018-0082>
19. McCloskey, D., & McDonnell, M. (2023). The Effect of Age-Progressed Avatars on Savings Behaviors for Retirement among Young People. In: Arai, K. (eds) *Proceedings of the Future Technologies Conference (FTC) 2023, Volume 4. FTC 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 816*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47448-4_19
20. *How AI could help modernize pension and retirement systems*. Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2024/11/how-ai-could-help-us-prevent-the-retirement-crisis/> (accessed 20 February 2023).
21. *This is minPension i Sverige AB*. Available at: <https://www.minpension.se/Media/MinPension/SVI/Dokument/This%20is%20minPension%20-%20in%20eng.pdf> (accessed 20 February 2023).

22. Dorofeev, M. L., & Knyazev, E. V. (2023). On the role of technological progress in the evolution of financial and investment models of pension provision for the population of Russia. *Financial life*, (3), 85–90. (in Russ.)
23. Ruggia-Frick, R. (2021). Applying emerging data-driven technologies in social security. Country experiences and ISSA guidelines. *Ubezpieczenia Społeczne. Teoria i praktyka*, 4, 31–49.
24. Cole, A., Ganju, S., & Kazam, M. (2023). Artificial intelligence and computer vision. *Real projects in Python, Keras, and TensorFlow*.
25. Lukyanenko, T. V. (2022). Artificial intelligence in mobile applications / Results of research work for 2021: Materials of the Anniversary scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Kuban State Agrarian University, Krasnodar, April 06, 2022 / Rep. for the release of A.G. Koshchayev. *Krasnodar, Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilina*, 444–446.
26. Ermolaev, S. S., Galiev, T. I., & Glebova, A. G. (2022). Features of modern Internet trading in international financial markets. *E-Management*, 5(3), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.26425/2658-3445-2022-5-3-90-97> (in Russ.)
27. Vasilyeva, E. V. (2023). Study of user experience of interaction of various target audiences with the portal interface. *E-Management*, 6(2), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.26425/2658-3445-2023-6-2-61-72> (in Russ.)
28. Lichtenstern, A., & Zagst, R. (2022). Optimal investment strategies for pension funds with regulation-conforming dynamic pension payment management in the absence of guarantees. *European Actuarial Journal*, 12, 647–700. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13385-021-00298-7>
29. Yang, F., & Wan, L. (2021). Pension Fund Financial Balance Model Under the Background of Artificial Intelligence. In: Abawajy, J., Xu, Z., Atiquzzaman, M., Zhang, X. (eds) *2021 International Conference on Applications and Techniques in Cyber Intelligence. ATCI 2021. Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies*, vol 81. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79197-1_119
30. Panda, A. C., Patnaik, A., Pawar, A., & Birari, A. (2023). Adoption of Fintech Towards Asset and Wealth Management: Understanding the Recent Scenario in India. In: Mishra, P., Sharma, A., Khanra, S., Kundu, S. K., Mishra, S. K. (eds) *Digital Economy Post COVID-19 Era. INDAM 2023. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-0197-5_23
31. Byrum, J. (2022). AI in Financial Portfolio Management: Practical Considerations and Use Cases. In: Babich, V., Birge, J. R., Hilary, G. (eds) *Innovative Technology at the Interface of Finance and Operations. Springer Series in Supply Chain Management*, vol 11. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75729-8_9

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